

The clinical studies of the treatment for all diseases drug J.A.F. fingal phases from 1-4.

Generated: 08/03/2025 2:38:45

Editorial Status: Submitted

Title and Additional Identifiers

Submission number

46963

Public title

The clinical studies of the treatment for all diseases drug J.A.F. fingal phases from 1-4.

Scientific Title

The clinical studies of the treatment for all diseases drug J.A.F. fingal phases from 1-4.

Acronym

The clinical studies of the treatment for all diseases drug J.A.F. fingal phases from 1-4.

EudraCT/CTIS number

No

IRAS number

No

ClinicalTrials.gov number

No

Secondary identifying numbers

No

Condition category

Date Applied

08/03/2025

Date Assigned

Last Edited

08/03/2025

Overall study Status

Completed

Recruitment status

No longer recruiting

Study Information

Study hypothesis

The studies build on the theory where all the diseases is the entropy stare in the major biochemistry molecules occupied by only the organic reactions mechanisms, when the drug is applied the all living organisms build from cells the intire of the cells become under the equilibrium and the state of all molecules will be send to the DNA as a divaiations not normals for it in the peak width of the IR spectra so the DNA will send radio waves to the materials and determined its major chemical formal then will make the proteins for the mechanism in organic chemistty to retyped the molecules to its major formula, then the drug will be active that is based on the mechanism of DNA and the proteins.

Ethics approval required

Ethics approval not required

Ethics approval(s)

Its for all diseases for all living organisms.

Study design

By the artificial intelligence under specific conditions focused on its rules.

Primary study design

Observational

Secondary study design

Case-control study

Study setting(s)

Internet/virtual

Study type(s)

Diagnostic, Prevention, Quality of life, Screening, Treatment, Safety, Efficacy

Overall study start date

01/03/2024

Overall study end date

01/02/2025

Condition

Completed accurately for all living organisms and all diseases as the levels from the chemicals to cells to all of the body.

Interventions

Its based on physical chemistry identifications and discovering of DNA and proteins and amino acids and nitrogen bases then physical chemistry of imaginary part and infomration programming device, then the biochemistry of the molecules, then pharmaceutical medicinal for the molecules and caffiene, then further for caffiene, iodine, and amino acids alanine to build the starting materials, then medicinal chemistry of the drug prepared, then signatory by biochemistry.

Intervention Type

Drug

Pharmaceutical study type(s)

Pharmacokinetic, Pharmacodynamic, Bioequivalence, Dose response, Pharmacogenetic, Pharmacogenomic, Pharmacoeconomic, Not Applicable

Phase

Phase IV

Drug/device/biological/vaccine name(s)

The drug name: J.A.F. fingal The device name: Abdul Kareem Biochemistry Programming Device. Biochemistry materials: Caffiene, Iodine, Amino acids.

Primary outcome measure

75%

Majored all the effects on the blood test materials for all living organisms for different times under specific accurate analysis.

Secondary outcome measures

80%

Majored all the effects on the blood test materials for all living organisms for different times under specific accurate analysis.

Study website

<https://accounts.osf.io/login?service=https%3A%2F%2Fosf.io%2F2e364%2F>

Participant information sheet

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Eligibility

Participant inclusion criteria

Only is randomly by AI for million one.

Participant type(s)

Healthy volunteer, Patient, Health professional, Carer, Employee, Learner/student, Resident, Population, Service user, All

Age group

Mixed

Lower age limit

1 Years

Upper age limit

70 Years

Sex

Both

Target number of participants

30000

Total final enrolment

30000

Participant exclusion criteria

There is only specific by AI, that focusing on all of the living organisms only randomly and that is which not randomly will go.

Recruitment start date

01/03/2023

Recruitment end date

01/03/2024

Locations**Countries of recruitment**

Jordan

Study participating centres**Study Centre****Study Centre Name**

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory, Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat

Address

Jordan, Almafraaq, Az-zunayah.

City

Almafraaq

Country

Jordan

Zip

+962

Plain English Summary

The studies build on the theory where all the diseases is the entropy stare in the major biochemistry molecules occupied by only the organic reactions mechanisms, when the drug is applied the all living organisms build from cells the intire of the cells become under the equilibrium and the state of all molecules will be send to the DNA as a divaiations not normals

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And it accurately by 75% for all living organisms for all diseases.

Results and Publications

Publication and dissemination plan

By my company and my specific name.

IPD sharing plan

There is no names for it as it by AI only.

Intention to publish date

01/01/2025

IPD sharing plan summary

Available on request

Contact(s)

Contact

Type(s)

Public, Scientific, Principal Investigator

Title

Mr

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Research organisation

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